

Synthesis and antibacterial activities of 1-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-2-amino/hydrazino-4-(*p*-nitrophenyl/*p*-chlorophenyl)-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thiones and related thiocarbamides, thiosemicarbazides and Schiff bases

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1-(*p*-Chlorophenyl)-2-benzylmercapto-4-(*p*-nitrophenyl/*p*-chlorophenyl)-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thiones (1) on treatment with ammonia/hydrazine hydrate under suitable conditions afford the corresponding 2-amino/hydrazino derivatives (2, 3). The latter on treatment with aryl isothiocyanates/aryl aldehydes afford the related thiocarbamides/thiosemicarbazides/Schiff bases (4-6) which have been tested for their antibacterial activity.

In view of the biological activities of Schiff bases¹ and *s*-triazines², it was of interest to synthesize these Schiff bases incorporating triazine moiety in addition to other class of biologically active compounds as given in the title.

This communication deals with the synthesis of 1-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-2-amino/hydrazino-4-(*p*-nitrophenyl/*p*-chlorophenyl)-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thiones (2, 3) and the corresponding *N*-[1-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-4-(*p*-nitrophenyl/*p*-chlorophenyl)-6-thioxo-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-2-yl]-thiocarbamides/thiosemicarbazides/Schiff bases (4-6).

and *S*-benzyl-*N*-(*p*-chlorophenyl)isothiourea. The amino/hydrazinotriazines (2, 3) were obtained in excellent yields when equimolar quantities of triazines (1) and saturated alcoholic ammonia/hydrazine hydrate were refluxed. The amino/hydrazinotriazines (2, 3) when treated with aryl isothiocyanates/aromatic aldehydes afforded the related thiocarbamides/thiosemicarbazides/Schiff bases (4-6)⁶ (Table 1).

Typically, the precursor 1-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-2-benzylmercapto-4-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thione (1a) was prepared^{3,4} from *p*-nitrobenzoyl isothiocyanate⁵

Table 1. Physical data of compounds 4-6*

Compd no.	Ar	Ar'	M.p °C
4a	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	212
b	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	217
c	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	237
d	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	196
e	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	188
f	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	174
g	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	182
h	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	222
i	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	219
j	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	230
k	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	208
l	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	211
m	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	199
n	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	189
5a	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	204
b	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	202
c	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	205
d	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	198
e	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	192
f	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	188
g	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	187
h	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	184
i	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	207
j	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	211
k	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	197
l	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	199
m	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	221

Table-1 (contd.)

n	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	227
o	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	179
p	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	186
6a	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	200
b	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	196
c	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	220
d	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	200
e	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	169
f	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	185
g	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	173
h	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	210
i	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	211
j	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	195
k	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	210
l	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	186
m	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	183
n	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	189
o	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	190
p	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	192

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined using a Köfler hot-stage apparatus and are uncorrected. NMR spectra were obtained on a Jeol FX-90Q spectrometer with TMS as an internal standard and IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 720 spectrophotometer. C, H and N were analyzed with a Perkin-Elmer 240C microanalyzer.

p-Nitrobenzoyl and *p*-chlorobenzoyl isothiocyanates were prepared by the reported method⁵. 2-Benzylmercapto-1-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-4-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thione (**1a**) was prepared from *p*-nitrobenzoyl isothiocyanate (10.4 g, 50 mmol) and *S*-benzyl-*N*-(*p*-chlorophenyl)isothiourea (13.85 g, 50 mmol) with stirring in benzene for 1 h and the resulting yellow solid was crystallized from benzene (13.8 g, 59%), m.p. 215–218° (Found : C, 56.92; H, 3.31; N, 11.91; S, 13.59. C₂₂H₁₅ClN₄O₂S₂ calcd. for : C, 56.53; H, 3.21; N, 11.99; S, 13.70%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 1630 (C=N), 1040 (C=S), 670 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); δ (CDCl₃) 4.52 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.35–7.71 (11H, m, ArH), 8.35–8.51 (2H, m, ArH).

Similarly, 2-benzylmercapto-1,4-bis(*p*-chlorophenyl)-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thione (**1b**) was prepared (61%), m.p. 174° (Found : C, 57.61; H, 3.26; N, 9.23; S, 14.21. C₂₂H₁₅Cl₂N₃S₂ calcd. for : C, 57.76; H, 3.28; N, 9.19; S, 14.00%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 1635 (C=N), 1090 (C=S), 680 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); δ (CDCl₃) 4.40 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.70–8.20 (11H, m, ArH), 8.42–8.50 (2H, m, ArH).

2-Amino-1-(p-chlorophenyl)-4-(p-nitrophenyl)-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thione (2a) : A solution of **1a** (9.34 g, 20 mmol) in absolute ethanol saturated with ammonia (70 ml) was refluxed for 6 h with stirring. Alcoholic ammonia was added in portions (10 ml) from time to time to keep the reaction mixture ammoniacal. It was then cooled, and the resulting solid was washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and benzene and crystallized from ethanol (4.3 g, 60%), m.p. 217° (Found : C, 50.0; H, 2.62; N, 19.51; S,

8.73. C₁₅H₁₀ClN₅O₂S calcd. for : C, 50.1; H, 2.77; N, 19.44; S, 8.88%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3305, 3140 (NH₂), 1645 (C=N), 1165 cm⁻¹ (C=S), δ (*d*₆-DMSO) 3.46 (2H, s, NH₂, exchangeable), 7.00–7.64 (8H, m, ArH).

Similarly, 2-amino-1,4-bis(*p*-chlorophenyl)-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thione (**2b**) was prepared (58%), m.p. 228–230° (Found : C, 51.63; H, 2.95; N, 15.98; S, 9.22. C₁₅H₁₀Cl₂N₄S calcd. for : C, 51.57; H, 2.86; N, 16.04; S, 9.16%); ν_{\max} 3405, 3203 (NH₂), 1635 (C=N), 1090 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (*d*₆-DMSO) 3.42 (2H, s, NH₂, exchangeable), 7.2–7.8 (8H, m, ArH).

1-(p-Chlorophenyl)-2-hydrazino-4-(p-nitrophenyl)-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thione (3a) : A mixture of **1a** (9.34 g, 20 mmol) in benzene (300 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (1.0 g, 20 mmol) was stirred at room temperature for 8 h, then filtered and washed with excess of petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) to remove benzyl mercaptan. The resulting solid was crystallized from ethanol/DMF (4 : 1), (4.7 g, 65%), m.p. 187° (Found : C, 48.23; H, 2.91; N, 22.47; S, 8.39. C₁₅H₁₁ClN₆O₂S calcd. for : C, 48.0; H, 2.93; N, 22.41; S, 8.53%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3440 (NHNH₂), 1630 (C=N), 1090 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (CDCl₃) 4.60 (3H, s, NHNH₂) 7.20–8.10 (8H, m, ArH).

Similarly, 1,4-bis(*p*-chlorophenyl)-2-hydrazino-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thione (**3b**) was synthesized (70%), m.p. 221–223° (Found : C, 49.53; H, 2.95; N, 19.17; S, 8.82. C₁₅H₁₁Cl₂N₅S calcd. for : C, 49.45; H, 3.02; N, 19.23; S, 8.79%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3400 (NHNH₂), 1635 (C=N), 1109 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (CDCl₃) 5.7 (3H, s, NHNH₂), 7.20–8.10 (8H, m, ArH).

N-(p-Methoxyphenyl)-N'-[1-(p-chlorophenyl)-4-(p-nitrophenyl)-6-thio-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl]thiocarbamide (4e) : A mixture of **2a** (1.8 g, 5 mmol) and *p*-methoxyphenyl isothiocyanate (0.99 g, 6 mmol) in benzene was refluxed for 1.5 h. The resulting solid was crystallized from ethanol (1.6 g, 61%), m.p. 188° (Found : C, 52.59; H, 3.44; N, 16.21; S, 12.41. C₂₃H₁₇ClN₆O₃S₂ calcd. for : C, 52.57; H, 3.23; N, 16.00; S, 12.19%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3380 (NH), 1615 (C=N), 1095 (C=S), 1530 cm⁻¹ (N-CS-N); δ (*d*₆-DMSO) 2.65 (2H, s, NH, exchangeable), 4.52 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.12–8.45 (12H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds (**4a-n**) were synthesized in 68–86% yields (Table 1).

N-(p-Anisyl)-N'-[1-(p-chlorophenyl)-4-(p-nitrophenyl)-6-thio-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl]thiosemicarbazide (5f) : A solution of **3a** (1.8 g, 5 mmol) and *p*-methoxyphenyl isothiocyanate (0.99 g, 6 mmol) in benzene was refluxed for 45 min, then washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and crystallized from ethanol (1.9 g, 70%), m.p. 188° (Found : C, 51.45; H, 3.29; N, 18.61; S, 11.77. C₂₃H₁₈ClN₇O₃S calcd. for : C, 51.11; H, 3.33; N, 18.14; S, 11.85%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3280, 3100 (NH), 1520 (N-C(=S)-

N). 1640 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (d_6 -DMSO) 4.52 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.00–8.44 (12H, m, ArH), 8.56–8.73 (2H, d, NHNH), 9.93 (1H, s, NH).

Similarly, other thiosemicarbazides (**5a-p**) were synthesized in 59–87% yields (Table 1).

N-[1-(*p*-Chlorophenyl)-4-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-6-thioxo-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl]-*N'*-(*p*-chlorobenzylidene)hydrazine (**6a**): A mixture of ethanolic solution of **3a** (3.6 g, 10 mmol) and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde (1.4 g, 10 mmol) was refluxed for 3 h. It was then filtered and the filtrate allowed to cool overnight. The resulting fine yellow crystals were crystallized from ethanol. (3.5 g, 70%), m.p. 200° (Found : C, 53.11; H, 2.73; N, 16.89; S, 6.51. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{14}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{S}$ calcd. for : C, 53.01; H, 2.81; N, 16.89; S, 6.42%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3340 (NH), 1630 (C=N), 1080 cm^{-1} (C=S); δ (CDCl_3) 4.57 (1H, s, NH, exchangeable), 7.19–8.00 (12H, m, ArH), 8.45 (1H, s, N=CH).

Similarly, other compounds (**6b-p**) were obtained in 63–76% yields (Table 1).

Antibacterial activity : The compounds (Table 1) were screened for antibacterial activity using cup-plate method at 100 and 500 ppm concentrations against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*,

S. albus and *B. subtilis*. Compounds **6a**, **6i** and **6m** were found to have moderate activity against the different strains.

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